

ANALYTICAL MODELLING AND FE SIMULATION OF IMPACT RESPONSE AND DAMAGE GROWTH IN A THIN-PLY LAMINATE

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ABSTRACT

Thin-ply composites offer reduced or suppressed matrix cracking and higher strains to first ply failure. Initial tests indicate a significantly different impact damage than for conventional composites, with less delamination and more fibre fracture. The current paper presents models focused on the observed fibre damage, including an analytical model for the response and damage initiation during impact on thin ply composites as well as a finite element FE model for prediction of damage growth. The limitations and challenges of the analytical model and FE model are discussed and illustrated by comparisons with response histories and fractography for drop weight impact on a thin-ply composite laminate.

1 INTRODUCTION

Matrix cracking in multidirectional laminates with sufficiently thin plies is constrained by the surrounding plies. The resulting “in-situ strength” increases with decreasing ply thickness [1]. Thus, thin-ply composites offer reduced or suppressed matrix cracking and higher strains to first ply failure and have attracted significant interest recently [2, 3]. On the other hand the delayed matrix cracking decreases the span between first and last ply failure, and causes a more brittle failure.

Textile preforms allow many manufacturing routes, e.g. autoclaving of prepregs, vacuum infusion or resin impregnation by resin transfer moulding (RTM). RTM offers higher production speed, which is crucial for the automotive industry. TeXtreme, produced by the Swedish company Oxeon is a thin-ply textile preform consisting of a plain weave made from thin and wide bands of spread tow material. This results in very low crimp and higher strength and stiffness than for conventional textiles, Fig. 1.

Impact damage resistance is a key issue for composite structures. Recent tests on epoxy impregnated carbon fibre TeXtreme cross-ply laminates, performed within the Swedish national project UpInTheBlue, indicated that impact damage involved significantly less delaminations and more fibre damage than in conventional composites [3].

Figure 1: Regular tow weave vs. spread tow weave thickness

The failure sequence during impact on laminates with conventional plies typically involves matrix cracking, followed by delamination and finally tensile fibre failure due to membrane strains caused by

large deflections after delamination. Fibre failures generated by membrane stresses tend to be fairly uniformly distributed over the laminate thickness. In contrast the fractography of a thin ply laminate [3] indicated a bending induced fibre failure, with more fibre fracture further from the midplane. Furthermore, more fibre fracture was observed on the side loaded in compression, as to be expected from the lower compressive strength in the fibre direction.

Analytical models for impact response and damage formation of conventional laminates typically focus on delamination initiation and growth [4], and are terminated when analytical criteria indicate fibre rupture [5]. To model impact on thin ply laminates an alternative analytical model has been developed for impact on plates where the failure occurs by bending rather than by delamination and membrane failure, [6].

Thin-ply laminates also offer significant challenges for computational modelling, as the number of plies is significantly larger than in conventional laminates. Thus a 4 mm thick laminate with a 100 gsm (g/m^2) TeXtreme weave consists of 44 weave plies, i.e. 88 layers of spread tow bands.

The following analysis was carried out within the European Air TN project DAMTEX, which is a collaboration between Swerea SICOMP and Oxeon in Sweden and Aernnova and University of Girona in Spain. It aims to develop methods to predict damage growth in thin-ply textile composites, and to demonstrate the applicability of the methods for impact damage tolerance in the aircraft industry. The experimental results are, however, taken from previous tests on cross-ply laminates in UpInTheBlue, as the experimental work on the quasi-isotropic layups in DAMTEX is not yet completed.

This paper presents a validation of the analytical model in [6] by comparison with a detailed finite element (FE) simulation and previous experiments on cross-ply laminates. Limitations and challenges of the models are discussed, as a foundation for further work in DAMTEX on modelling of more general layups with thin plies.

2 ANALYTICAL MODEL

The analytical model considers bending of a rectangular simply supported orthotropic plate under a central quasi-static contact load, Fig. 2, including approximate expressions for shear deformation, contact indentation and stiffening due to large deflection membrane effects. The quasi-static solution is applicable for all cases where the impactor mass is at least twice the mass of the impacted plate [7]. In such cases the impact response is most conveniently shown as a load-deflection curve.

Figure 2: Geometry and coordinates for a plate under a central contact load.

Criteria were provided for initiation of shear cracking, bending failure, delamination and fibre rupture (“penetration”) due to membrane strains at large deflections [6]. An initiation criterion for growth of the bending damage zone was presented using a fracture mechanics solution for cracked plates loaded by bending moments.

The load for initiation of shear failure is given by:

$$F_s = \frac{4}{3} \sqrt{R/Q_c} (\pi h \tau_U)^{3/2} \quad \text{where } \tau_U = \text{Min}\{XZ, YZ^*\} \quad (1)$$

where XZ is the shear strength of the ply under shear stress τ_{13} and YZ^* is the effective shear strength of the ply under shear stress τ_{23} . For a multidirectional laminate YZ^* is given by:

$$\text{Multidirectional laminate: } YZ^* = \text{Max}\{YZ_{IS1}, YZ_{IS2}\} \quad (2)$$

$$\text{where } YZ_{IS1} \approx 1.12\sqrt{2} \cdot Y_t \quad YZ_{IS2} \approx 1.4\sqrt{G_{Ic}^{Yt} E_2 / [2(1 + \nu_{23})t]}$$

The delamination threshold load F_{dth} is given by:

$$F_{dth} = F_{d1} = \pi\sqrt{32G_{Ic} D^* / 3} \quad (3)$$

The critical load F_r for rupture (tearing) of the fibres in the laminate is given by:

$$F_r = 4\pi R h E_r^* \varepsilon_{lt}^2 / (1 - \nu_r^*) \quad (4)$$

where E_r^* and ν_r^* are the average membrane Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio in membrane loading of the laminate, and ε_{lt} is the tensile failure strain of fibres in the laminate.

Failure in bending was determined by considering the solution for a simply supported rectangular quasi-isotropic plate under a concentrated central load within a small radius c , where the relation between bending moments M_x and M_y and contact load F are given by:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} M_x(x, r) &= \frac{F}{4\pi} \left[(1 + \nu_{r\theta}) \ln\left(\frac{2}{\pi} b/r\right) - (1 - \nu_{r\theta}) x^2/r^2 \right] \\ M_y(x, r) &= \frac{F}{4\pi} \left[(1 + \nu_{r\theta}) \ln\left(\frac{2}{\pi} b/r\right) + (1 - \nu_{r\theta}) x^2/r^2 \right] \end{aligned} \right\} \begin{aligned} &M_x(c, c) \\ &M_y(c, c) \end{aligned} \quad \left. \begin{aligned} &r \geq c \\ &r < c \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (5)$$

where r is the distance to the load centre. The quantity x^2/r^2 is 1 on the x -axis and 0 on the y -axis. Note that the solution in [6] contained a typo, which has been corrected in Eq (5) above. For the current cross-ply laminate Eq. (5) is obviously only an approximation. Inspection of Eq. (5) reveals that the largest moment will be M_y along the x -axis.

The contact radius c is given by the following expression:

$$c = \left(\frac{3}{4} RF / Q_c\right)^{1/3} \quad \text{where } 1/Q_c = 1/Q_{zi} + 1/Q_{zp} \quad \text{and } Q_{zk} \approx E_{zk} / (1 - \nu_{rzk} \nu_{zrk}) \quad (6)$$

where R is the impactor tip radius, Fig. 2.

For linear elastic conditions the stress distribution of a homogenous laminate is linear through the laminate, and the moment may be expressed as follows:

$$M = \sigma_{\max} \cdot h^2 / 6 \quad (7)$$

Failure first occurs in compression, and hence the critical moment for initiation of compressive failure in a laminate with homogenised compressive strength X_{hc} is given by:

$$M_c = X_{hc} \cdot h^2 / 6 \quad (8)$$

Local compressive failure allows continued crushing at more or less constant stress, while tensile failure is more or less brittle. Hence, compressive failure on the upper side of the laminate will merely cause a redistribution of stresses until the homogenised tensile strength X_{ht} is reached on the lower side of the laminate. Further tensile failure will cause a decreasing moment.

The stress distribution at tensile failure may be obtained by considering horizontal equilibrium of a laminate in bending, Fig. 3. Solution of the equilibrium equations provides the thickness fractions s_c , s_0 and s_t experiencing inelastic crushing, elastic compression and elastic tension, respectively.

$$s_c = 1/[1 + 2/(X_{ht}/X_{hc} - 1)] \quad s_0 = (1 - s_c)/(X_{ht}/X_{hc} + 1) \quad s_t = 1 - s_c - s_0 \quad (9)$$

The limiting moment M_t for tensile failure is now given by

$$M_t = f_{Mt} X_{ht} h^2 / 6 \quad \text{where } f_{Mt} = 3(s_c^2 + 2s_c s_0) X_{hc} / X_{ht} + 2(s_t^2 + s_0^3 / s_t) \quad (10)$$

Figure 3: Stress distribution

The critical load for initiation of compressive and tensile failure is obtained by combining Eq. (5) and Eq. (6) and solving iteratively for F when the largest moment initiates failure. The corresponding loads F_c and F_t for compressive and tensile failure are defined by:

$$F = F_c \Rightarrow M_y(0,0) = M_c \quad F = F_t \Rightarrow M_y(0,0) = M_t \quad (11)$$

Under plane stress with a bending crack (assuming complete loss of stiffness when X_{ht} is reached) of half length L the maximum tensile strain energy release rate due to bending is given by:

$$G_b = K_b^2/E = \sigma_b^2 \pi L/E \quad \text{where } \sigma_{bc} = 6M/h^2 \quad \text{and} \quad \sigma_{bt} = (6M/h^2)/f_{Mt} \quad (12)$$

3 EXPERIMENTAL STUDY

As part of the UpInTheBlue project low-speed impact tests and post-damage analysis was performed on specimens manufactured with TeXtreme 100 gsm thin ply cross ply weaves. Six specimens were impacted with either 30 or 21 J and afterwards scanned with ultrasound to investigate the delaminations. After that the specimens were either sectioned, in order to study matrix cracks and delaminations, or deplieed, to study the fibre failures layer by layer.

3.1 Specimens

The fibre preform material used to manufacture all specimens was a TeXtreme® spread tow fabric provided by Oxeon, Sweden. Each fabric ply is a plain weave composed of 20 mm wide carbon fibre bands oriented along the 0° and 90° directions as shown in the right part of Fig. 1.

The specimens were manufactured by SICOMP using 44 layers of 100 gsm TeXtreme cross-ply weave impregnated with an LY556 Araldite epoxy matrix. Each layer is 0.092 mm thick and consists of woven 0.046 mm thick UD bands. The fibre layers were placed so that crossing-points of the weave were all on top of each other with fibres only in the 0° and 90° directions, i.e. the layup was $(0^\circ/90^\circ)_{44}$, where the curved bracket corresponds to a single weave layer.

The specimens were manufactured by Resin Transfer Moulding (RTM). All specimens were 151x101 mm in size and 4.04 ± 0.01 mm thick. As RTM was used both surfaces of the laminates were smooth and very little variation in thickness could be measured.

The specimens were cut out from large plates which were infused using a pressure of 2 to 4 bars and a mould temperature of 50°C during mould filling and 80°C during curing. The plates spent a total of 15 h in the mould, and were then post-cured in an oven in 140°C for 4 hours.

Six specimens were manufactured and were impacted at different locations with different impact energies and afterwards subjected to different post-damage destructive analyses.

The results for the specimen impacted with 30 J were used for comparison with the numerical models developed in this study.

3.2 Impact tests

The impact tests were done according to ASTM D7136 [8] except that the rubber clamps were placed over the corners of the 125x75 mm impact window to eliminate edge moments, Fig. 4.

Figure 4: Impact rig and equipment

All specimens were impacted with a 3.09 kg mass having a 12.5 mm radius hemispherical tup, using different impact velocities to achieve the desired impact energy. The plain weave results in a “checker board” square pattern. To investigate the influence of impact location in the weave pattern the specimens were either impacted in the intersection (X) of four squares, or in the centre (C) of one of the squares, Fig. 5. The corresponding specimen numbers contained an initial X or C.

Figure 5: Specimen dimensions and impact position

During impact the force was recorded using a Dytran 1203V5 piezoelectric ring sensor attached to the impactor assembly behind the impactor tup. The deflection of the underside of the specimen was recorded using an MEL M70LL/10 laser distance sensor. To increase the accuracy of the laser a piece of white matte tape was attached to the underside of the specimen. The speed of the impactor assembly just before impact was registered using a photo sensor which recorded the passing of a photo flag consisting of a 4 mm diameter steel rod attached to the impactor assembly.

All the instrumentation was connected to a PicoScope 4424 digital oscilloscope which recorded the signals during the impact events. The data was subsequently saved to a PC for further processing.

3.3 Fractography

After impact each specimen was analysed with ultrasound and subjected to one of two destructive fractographic methods, i.e. deplying or sectioning.

Deplying was done to investigate the fibre failures layer by layer. This was done by first burning most (but not all) of the matrix by putting the specimens in an oven at 380°C for 1 h. After that each layer could be separated individually and scanned using a regular scanner. The image files obtained from scanning were then processed via computer software to clearly mark the fibre failures.

Sectioning was done to investigate the delaminations and matrix cracks through the thickness. The specimens were sectioned through the impact location and the area around the impact was encased in

fluorescent epoxy and afterwards polished. These sections were then studied in an optical microscope, filters were used which clearly indicated where the fluorescent epoxy had penetrated the delaminations and cracks left after impact.

4 MATERIAL DATA

4.1 Weave material

For the present layout the principal axes of the weave coincide with the x - y - z coordinates of the laminate. The homogenised mechanical properties of the TeXtreme plain weave material are presented in Table 1. Properties in italics are assumed, while the remaining properties have been reported in [3]. E_z was not measured but is assumed equal to E_2 measured for unidirectional (UD) weave bands, [3].

$E_x = E_y$	E_z	G_{xy}	$G_{xz} = G_{yz}$	ν_{xy}	$\nu_{xz} = \nu_{yz}$	$X_{ht} = Y_{ht}$	$X_{hc} = Y_{hc}$
69.1 GPa	8.1 GPa	5.5 GPa	<i>4 GPa</i>	0.033	<i>0.3</i>	1260 MPa	709 MPa

Table 1: Mechanical properties of 100 gsm Textreme®-weave.

4.1 Material in UD-plyies

The finite element model was based on modelling the weave plyies as sublaminates with a $0^\circ/90^\circ$ layout. The properties of the assumed constituent UD plyies were based on tests performed on UD laminates made from the bands of the TeXtreme® weave, except for the in-plane fracture toughness. The results are reported Table 2. The toughness in fibre tension G_{cFT} was obtained from [9], while the toughness in fibre compression G_{cFC} was obtained from [6]. Since a large difference exists between reported values of G_{cFC} , the two extreme values were used to determine their influence on the structural response and damage of the specimen, while the toughness in transverse tension G_{cMT} was assumed equal to the interlaminar toughness G_{Ic} . In addition, the influence of the ply thickness and position in the laminate on its strength (in-situ strength) is also considered. The calculated in-situ strength for Y_t , S_L and S_T are reported in brackets in Table 2. The in-situ value for Y_t^{is} includes the reduction for manufacturing induced residual stresses (26 MPa). Material data for G_{23} , ν_{23} and G_{cMC} was not available and has been assumed, which is indicated by numbers in italics. Initiation values were used for the interlaminar toughness G_{Ic} , which showed a strong increase with delamination growth. ENF tests indicated G_{IIc} values of 2.9 kJ/m² or more, but may have been influenced by multiple crack planes. Use of the relation derived in [10] results in $G_{IIc} = 3.1 \cdot G_{Ic} = 1.6$ kJ/m².

	E_1	$E_2 = E_3$	$G_{12} = G_{13}$	G_{23}	$\nu_{12} = \nu_{13}$	ν_{23}
[GPa]	130	8.1	6.3	<i>4</i>	0.25	<i>0.45</i>
	X_t	X_c	Y_t	Y_c	S_L	S_T
[MPa]	2390	1272	50 (210*)	146	57 (163*)	57 (163*)
	G_{cFT}	G_{cFC}	G_{cMT}	G_{cMC}	G_{Ic}	G_{IIc}
[kJ/m ²]	90 [9]	26 or 61 [6]	0.5	<i>1.5</i>	0.5	2.9 or 1.6

Table 2: Mechanical properties UD bands in 100 gsm Textreme®-weave. * = In-situ properties

The in-situ strength related to the material and laminate used in the study were calculated by applying the equations for the in-situ effects presented in [11] and [12]. Since most plyies are thin and embedded (86 plyies out of 88), only the formulations for this type of configuration were used in the analysis, i.e. the two outer plyies were given in-situ strength values of embedded plyies.

$$Y_t^{is} = \sqrt{4G_{Ic}E_2/\pi} \quad (13)$$

$$S_L^{is} = \sqrt{\left[\left(1 + \beta 48G_{Ic}G_{12}^2/\pi \right)^{1/2} - 1 \right] / (3\beta G_{12})} \quad (14)$$

The shear stress-strain relation was approximated by the following equation:

$$\gamma_{12} = \sigma_{12}/G_{12} + \beta\sigma_{12}^3 \quad (15)$$

The experimental shear curve was fitted by using $\beta=3.5 \cdot 10^{-8}/\text{MPa}^3$, as illustrated by Fig. 6.

Figure 6: Fitting to the experimental shear stress-strain curve

5 FINITE ELEMENT MODEL

The commercial finite element (FE) software ABAQUS was used for all numerical analyses carried out in this study. The solver ABAQUS Implicit/Dynamic was chosen for the impact analysis. The reason for choosing the implicit solver is the wish to compare Hashin with LaRC05 failure criteria for thin-ply laminates. The composite lay-up functionality is not available for solid elements in ABAQUS Explicit, and hence it was decided to run the entire numerical analysis with ABAQUS Implicit/Dynamic, where composite lay-up is available both for continuum shell elements (Hashin) and for solid elements (LaRC05).

The laminate was modelled using continuum shell elements (SC8R), with one single element through the thickness. The continuum shell section was defined using the composite lay-up formulation in ABAQUS, where the inputs include number of layers, material type and fibre orientation for each layer, and individual layer thicknesses.

The textile architecture was not considered. Instead, the cross-ply weave was modelled using two unidirectional plies of half the thickness of the weave ($t_{UD} = 0.046$ mm; $t_{weave} = 0.092$ mm). This yields a total number of 88 plies instead of 44 weave plies used to manufacture the specimen.

The part was meshed using 4000 structured hexahedral elements, with identical element size of 2 mm x 2 mm covering the whole specimen. It was verified that this element size was not greater than the maximum element size recommended for the material used in the study.

The impact energy was set to 31.7 J, and was obtained by specifying an initial velocity of 4.53 m/s with a drop mass weight of 3.09 kg, modelled as a rigid body hemisphere with 12.5 mm radius.

The contact between the laminate and the impactor was defined as a surface to surface interaction with hard contact law.

No damage stabilization in forms of a viscosity coefficient was used in the material data input. However, moderate dissipation option was chosen in the step definition in order to reduce solution noise and improve convergence behaviour without significantly degrading solution accuracy.

Figure 7 illustrates definitions of the geometry and boundary conditions in the numerical model. A line square underneath the specimen, representing the support edges of the impact window (125 mm x

75 mm), restricts the vertical displacement along z . The four clamps on the top face of the specimen were modelled by restricting z -displacement of the four corner nodes. The centre node on the top face of the specimen has its only degree of freedom along the z direction. Finally, the impactor is only allowed to translate along the z axis, using a predefined field for the initial velocity.

Due to the cross-ply lay-up of the specimen, a quarter model with symmetry along x -axis and y -axis was also considered. This configuration yields shorter computing time for identical results.

Figure 7. Geometry and boundary conditions of the FE model.

The damage initiation and growth is calculated based on the work by Hashin [13-14], available as a material input window in ABAQUS. It was chosen to use $\alpha=0$ to determine the fibre tensile initiation criterion, i.e. the shear stress was not considered to compute the fibre failure criterion in tension.

The initiation criteria for fibre tension and compression, and matrix tension and compression are shown in Eqs. (16)-(17).

$$F_f^t = (\sigma_{11}/X_t)^2 \text{ for } \sigma_{11} \geq 0 \quad \text{and} \quad F_f^c = (\sigma_{11}/X_t)^2 \text{ for } \sigma_{11} < 0 \quad (16)$$

$$F_m^t = (\sigma_{22}/Y_t)^2 + (\tau_{12}/S_L) \quad \text{for } \sigma_{22} \geq 0 \quad \text{and} \quad (17)$$

$$F_m^c = (\sigma_{22}/2S_T)^2 + \left[(Y_c/2S_T)^2 - 1 \right] (\sigma_{22}/Y_c) + (\tau_{12}/S_L) \quad \text{for } \sigma_{22} < 0$$

The progressive degradation of the material is controlled by the individual fracture energies of matrix and fibre in the tensile and compression direction. The failure initiates when the strength criteria reach a value of 1. The damage evolution variable, d_m , which indicates the level of damage in an element, is a function of the strain at failure, undamaged material stiffness, and the current value of the failure initiation variable. The element ply is fully damaged when d_m reaches 1.

6 COMPARISON OF MODELS AND EXPERIMENTS

In the analytical model the load-deflection relation up to damage initiation is given by the bending deflection for a centrally loaded simply supported orthotropic plate, and an approximation for the additional shear deformation, as explained in [6]. The analytical model predicts the following loads for failure initiation in out-of-plane shear, fibre compression, fibre tension, delamination and penetration:

$$F_s = 1.0 \text{ kN} \quad F_c = 5.5 \text{ kN} \quad F_t = 9.0 \text{ kN} \quad F_{dth} = 9.1 \text{ or } 6.7 \text{ kN} \quad F_r = 14.9 \text{ kN}$$

Figure 8a shows predicted stresses and strain energy release rate for the predicted loads for onset of compressive failure F_c and tensile failure F_t . Figure 8b shows a comparison between the experimentally observed load-deflection of specimen X1 and the analytical model with the loads F_c and F_r . From Fig. 8a it is evident that fibre fracture will occur along the x -axis, and that the values of G are large enough to allow initial damage growth. The model in Fig. 8b can only predict damage

initiation, but any damage growth will cause a decreasing stiffness and hence a decreasing load.

Figure 8: Analytical prediction of stresses, G and load vs deflection, and comparison with experiment

The FE model was first used to study the influence of fracture toughness in fibre compression G_{cFC} (61 or 26 kJ/m²). It was observed that the models considering a higher G_{cFC} overestimated the maximum load by more than 20%. Therefore, all remaining analyses were run with $G_{cFC} = 26$ kJ/m².

Figure 9 shows a comparison of FE simulations and experimental response for specimen X1 in terms of time-load history and load-deflection curve. The deflection was defined as the displacement of the back face immediately below the point of impact. The predicted loads for fibre damage onset are 6.6 kN in compression and 7.4 kN in tension, corresponding to F_c and F_t in the analytical model. The damage growth predicted by the in-situ model in fibre tension (FT), fibre compression (FC), matrix tension (MT) and matrix compression (MC) is shown in Fig. 10.

Figure 9: Impact response. Comparison between FE simulation and experiments

Figure 10: FE predictions of fibre and matrix damage for in-situ strength.

The corresponding final damage predicted using bulk material strengths is illustrated Fig. 11, which also includes a comparison of the dissipated energy in experiments and in the two FE models.

Figure 11: FE prediction of fibre and matrix damage using bulk strength, and energy dissipation.

Both the FE model using bulk material strength and in-situ strength predict with a fairly good accuracy the first load peak of 7.7 kN at 0.9 ms (or 2.7 mm deflection). Before that point no significant difference exists between the numerical model that considers bulk data and the one that considers in-situ data but we can observe a clear difference between the two models right after the maximum load is reached. The model with in-situ strength has a load increase, while the model with bulk data has a lower load level, more similar to the loads observed in the experiments. However, in contrast to the predictions of the bulk material model in Fig. 11 the experimental observations using optical microscopy indicated very limited matrix cracking, as illustrated by Fig. 12.

Figure 12: Matrix cracks and delaminations through the thickness (20 J impacted X2 specimen) - few cases of matrix (shear) cracking. Original picture (lower) and after processing for increased contrast.

Figure 13 gives a comparison between the predicted (using in-situ properties) and experimentally observed projection of fibre damage in all plies, as well as delaminations observed by C-scan.

Figure 13: In-plane distribution of fibre damage as predicted by FE and observed by deploying. Delaminations observed by C-scan are included in grey.

Figure 14 shows a detailed comparison of fractographic observations and the model predictions of the fibre damage in the x - z and y - z planes, where the impact occurred in the centre of the upper side.

Figure 14: Comparison of predicted and observed fibre damage through the thickness. Experiments in blue, theory in red, FE in black/gray (fully/partially damaged fibres).

7 DISCUSSION

It is evident that fibre failure is essential and significant for the thin ply laminates in the current study, while delamination is less significant than in conventional laminates. The distribution of fibre fracture through the laminate thickness illustrates that fibre failure was induced by bending prior to delamination. The delamination zone is relatively narrow and appears to follow the directions of major fibre cracks, which indicates that delaminations were initiated by fibre fracture. Two models that focus on in-plane damage and exclude delamination have been suggested to cope with the large number of plies and interfaces. It is not yet clear if the failure sequence with fibre failure prior to delamination is due to high interlaminar toughness or due to suppressed matrix cracking in thin ply laminates.

The analytical model is capable of predicting the elastic behaviour, the onset of fibre compressive fracture and the peak load for ultimate tensile failure, as well as the distribution of fibre fracture through the laminate.

Similar results are obtained from the FE model, which also was able to predict the subsequent growth and distribution of fibre fracture with good accuracy. A better match of the load-deflection curve was obtained by using matrix dominated strengths of bulk material, rather than in-situ strengths of thin plies, but the amount of matrix cracking is grossly overestimated in comparison to fractography, where very little matrix cracking was observed. It is also noted that both the FE model with bulk properties and with in-situ properties dissipate significantly less energy in damage formation than what was observed in the experiments. This indicates that the disagreement with the experimental response was caused by neglect of delaminations, rather than by the use of in-situ strengths.

For more reliable prediction of damage and better agreement with load-deflection curves future FE models of thin ply laminates may have to include the interaction between fibre fracture and delaminations, but the large number of plies and interfaces poses a major computational challenge and calls for approaches to increase computational efficiency by judicious simplifications. In this context it is important to remember that delaminations and out-of-plane shear failure cannot be captured by the current modelling approach using layered solid or shell elements.

8 CONCLUSIONS

Fibre damage initiated by bending has been observed as a significant failure mode of a thin ply plain weave laminate, where delaminations were less prominent than in conventional laminates. The suggested analytical plate model and FE model, where delamination was neglected, were both able to predict the onset of fibre failure, and distribution of fibre failure through the thickness. The FE model was also able to accurately predict the extent of fibre fracture, but improved predictions of the response and energy dissipation will require inclusion of initiation and growth of delaminations induced by fibre fracture.

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